

Working Paper

Financial Oversight:
Internal and External Control Authorities

Pauline Thinus and Paul Dermine

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Abstract: Sound financial management constitutes a major challenge of the national recovery and resilience plans. The architects of NGEU and the RRF have sought a delicate balance between macroeconomic performance (and the rapid injections of funds in national economies) and the protection of the Union’s financial interests. The result is a singular compromise, which this Chapter seeks to unveil. On the one hand, the RRF is implemented in direct management, with the Member States as direct beneficiaries. On the other, recovery plans rest on an elaborate control and audit system *à la* shared management, which closely intertwines national and European apparati and is articulated around different procedural phases, placing national authorities and final recipients of recovery funds under tight and close scrutiny. The system also involves other supranational actors as external safeguards, namely the European Court of Auditors (ECA), the European Public Prosecutor’s Office (EPPO) and the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF)..

Keywords: financial oversight; financial interests of the EU; sound management; control and audit; economic governance; EU governance; RRF; NGEU

16.1 Introduction

With great financial powers comes great responsibility. For the 2021-2027 period, the long-term budget of the European Union (EU) amounts to more than EUR 2 trillion, among which the recovery plan ‘NextGenerationEU’ (NGEU) represents EUR 806.9 billion.² The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) encompasses almost the entirety of the initiative and is worth EUR 724.8 billion.³ This unprecedented strengthening of the Union’s budgetary capacity naturally comes with its own challenges. The sound management of the recovery funds, and the preservation of the Union’s financial interests is undeniably a prominent one, for various reasons. First, there is the general concern, valid for any type of EU funding, that public money should be well spent, in order to achieve its founding purposes. Specific

¹ Pauline Thinus is a PhD candidate in political science at Université Libre de Bruxelles. Paul Dermine is Professor of European Union Law at the Université Libre de Bruxelles.

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² All amounts are in 2023 prices. See European Commission, ‘The 2021-2027 EU budget – What’s new?’ <https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/2021-2027/whats-new_en> accessed 18 December 2023.

³ See Chapter 8 in this volume.

features of NGEU make the challenge of its sound financial management more acute. Beyond its sheer size, there is the fact that NGEU is the product of massive public borrowings, carried by the EU in its own name on the markets. This budgetary novelty carries new reputational demands. Second, NGEU is to be implemented against a tight and fairly rigid timeframe. Most notably, reforms and investments funded by NGEU should be completed within a five-year period, by end August 2026.⁴ NGEU moreover proceeds from a results-oriented, performance-based approach, under which EU monies are only disbursed if measures and reforms are successfully implemented at the national level. Third, as a result, NGEU puts great pressure on the administrative structures of the Union and, even more so, of its Member States. In the light of certain weaknesses already revealed in the context of the Union's structural funds,⁵ the adequacy of national absorption capacities of Member States has been questioned, especially vis-à-vis some of the main beneficiaries such as Italy.⁶ Fourth, the political context is also a key issue in some Member States, where rule of law backsliding,⁷ attacks on independent authorities and state capture entail increased risks of fraud, corruption and misappropriation of EU monies. Last but not least, the political value of NGEU should not be overlooked. The recovery plan is a major political initiative, resulting from difficult negotiations between Member States historically polarized on budgetary integration and economic solidarity.⁸ As such, and considering its *ad hoc*, temporary nature, it also constitutes a test for the EU. If successful, it could pave the way for a structural deepening of budgetary integration, through new permanent budgetary capacities.⁹ If it is a failure, it will nip those hopes in the bud. Results will primarily be gauged against the use made of NGEU funds, especially their allocation to their intended use as well as the timely and genuine implementation of agreed reforms and investments under the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs),¹⁰ in a nutshell, their sound management.

In this configuration, and against the broader background of the rise of 'governance through funding', financial accountability is decisive, and all actors involved in NGEU and RRF governance – EU institutions, EU bodies, national authorities – have to live up to these major challenges for the sound management of recovery funds and the protection of the Union's financial interests. This chapter examines these issues and explores the various control and oversight mechanisms designed to address them.

The Chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 first examines the specific features of the RRF framework which impact the oversight capacity of the EU and its members. Section 3 addresses the sharing of responsibilities between the European Commission and the Member States, in other words the national and European internal control systems. Lastly, Section 4 details the supporting role of Union's external control bodies: the European Court of Auditors (ECA), the European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO) and the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). Section 5 concludes.

⁴ RRF Regulation, Article 20(4)(d).

⁵ Cristian Incaltarau, Gabriela Pascariu, Neculai-Cristian Surubaru, 'Evaluating the determinants of EU funds absorption across old and new member states – the role of administrative capacity and political governance', *JCMS*, 2020, pp. 941-961.

⁶ On the Italian case, see Amy Kazmin, 'Will Italy squander its 200bn opportunity?', *Financial Times*, 30.8.2023.

⁷ See Chapter 13 in this volume.

⁸ See, for example, Markus Brunnermeier, Harold James, Jean-Pierre Landau, *The Euro and the Battle of Ideas*, Princeton University Press, 2016.

⁹ See Chapter 4 in this volume. See also Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity – Legal Integration after COVID-19 and the War in Ukraine*, Oxford, OUP, 2022.

¹⁰ See Chapter 10 in this volume.

16.2 The specificities of the RRF framework impacting oversight

This section introduces a number of important background considerations which frame the RRF and its financial oversight architecture. First, the principle of sound financial management and the protection of the EU's financial interests are introduced (2.1). Essential features of the RRF's financial management are then presented (2.2).

16.2.1 *The protection of the EU's financial interests through the RRF and the sound management of recovery funds*

The sound management of EU funds and the protection of the Union's financial interests are important principles of EU primary law,¹¹ which were naturally placed at the core of the Facility. Their respect is an obligation that is recalled several times in Regulation 2021/241 ('the RRF Regulation'). Recital 40 states that "the implementation of the Facility should be carried out in line with the principle of sound financial management", and Article 22 is the provision specifically dedicated to the protection of the Union's financial interests. Sound financial management essentially revolves around performance and principles of economy, efficiency and effectiveness according to the Financial Regulation¹². When it comes to the oversight of recovery funds, it consists in the avoidance of double funding,¹³ and the prevention of "serious irregularities", which include, according to Recital 53, "fraud, corruption and conflicts of interest in relation to the measures supported by the Facility."

In EU budgetary law, irregularities can cover "any infringement of a provision of Community law resulting from an act or omission by an economic operator, which has, or would have, the effect of prejudicing the general budget of the Communities or budgets managed by them."¹⁴ However, as Gadbled has aptly shown, the RRF legislation, like other important pieces of budgetary law, places the emphasis on "systemic" irregularities, which relate to the control and monitoring systems designed to protect the Union's financial interests by detecting and correcting specific infringements.¹⁵ Control frameworks play a crucial role in ensuring the regular use of EU funding. Their deficiencies create risks for the sound management of funds and consequently the financial interests of the Union, especially when they "are flawed to the point where irregularities have a high probability of occurrence."¹⁶ The entire EU legal framework organizing its budget is built upon the notions of risk and probability.¹⁷ The legislation organizing the RRF makes no exception and thus aims to prevent, detect and correct systemic irregularities thanks to well-functioning control and monitoring systems.

¹¹ See most notably Articles 310(5)(6), 317 and 325 TFEU

¹² Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2018/1046 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 July 2018 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union, amending Regulations (EU) No 1296/2013, (EU) No 1301/2013, (EU) No 1303/2013, (EU) No 1304/2013, (EU) No 1309/2013, (EU) No 1316/2013, (EU) No 223/2014, (EU) No 283/2014, and Decision No 541/2014/EU and repealing Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 966/2012 [2018] OJ L193, Article 33.

¹³ According to Recital 62 of the RRF Regulation, "reforms and investment projects financed under the Facility should be able to receive funding from other Union programmes and instruments provided that such support does not cover the same cost."

¹⁴ Council Regulation (EC, EURATOM) No 2988/95 of 18 December 1995 on the protection of the European Communities financial interests [1995] OJ L312, art 1(2).

¹⁵ Robin Gadbled, 'Addressing System Deficiencies in the Protection of the Financial Interests of the EU: Preventing Harm and Incentivizing Change', *German Law Journal* (2023), 24, 1023, 1023.

¹⁶ Gadbled (n 14) 1027.

¹⁷ Gadbled (n 14) 1026

Overall, to ensure sound management of recovery funds and the preservation of the Union's financial interests, the RRF has established a robust oversight framework, including both supranational and national actors; control systems, audit strategies, and their verification; as well as corrective mechanisms in case of serious irregularities, which are addressed in the following sections.

16.2.2 The RRF as a sui generis instrument of direct management

The RRF is based on milestones and targets listed in each NRRP.¹⁸ As a consequence, the RRF control and audit framework mainly focuses on the fulfilment of these milestones and targets.¹⁹ Such performance-based approach to EU spending in turn impacts the traditional approach to financial control and audit in the EU.

Yet, the main specificity of the RRF affecting financial oversight relates to its management template. Under Article 317 TFEU, the Commission assumes the responsibility to “implement the budget,” “in cooperation with the Member States,” and in accordance with the regulations adopted under Article 322 TFEU. EU budgetary law and, more specifically, the Financial Regulation,²⁰ admits three methods of budgetary implementation which differently impact the distribution of powers and responsibilities between the EU and the national level: direct management, under which the Commission immediately assumes budgetary implementation; shared management, under which implementation is ensured in cooperation with the Member States; and indirect management, where implementation is outsourced to third entities (such as EU agencies, third countries or other international organisations).

The RRF Regulation clearly states that the Facility is implemented in direct management,²¹ with Member States as direct beneficiaries of the funds.²² The choice of this modality was logical from a macroeconomic perspective, as it ensures maximal speed in the injection of the funds in Member States' economies, and thereby guarantees that NGEU will produce its stabilizing effect. However, beyond this formal characterization, the dominant view is that the implementation of the RRF should be approached as a *sui generis* form of direct management.²³ The main reason for such an approach lies in the nature of the immediate beneficiaries, i.e. the Member States and not, as normally the case under direct management, natural or legal persons and entities. Recovery funds are disbursed to national authorities, and it is through national budgets that they are channelled to final recipients.

As a consequence, the Commission also relies on Member States for financial control and audit, almost “as in shared management.”²⁴ This means that they are not only beneficiaries but also involved in the budgetary implementation. Quite tellingly, Recital 54 of the RRF Regulation makes clear that it is “primarily the responsibility” of Member States to ensure the

¹⁸ See Chapters 10 and 12 of this volume on NRRPs and milestones and targets respectively.

¹⁹ Velina Lilyanova, ‘Governance and oversight of the Recovery and Resilience Facility’, European Parliamentary Research Service, Briefing, PE.747.883, 8 May 2023, 3.

²⁰ Regulation 2018/1046, Article 62.

²¹ RRF Regulation, Article 8.

²² RRF Regulation, Article 22(1).

²³ See Clemens Kreith and Charlotte Arwidi ‘Protecting the EU's Financial Interests in the New Recovery and Resilience Facility the Role of the European Anti-Fraud Office’, *EUcrim*, 3/2021, 171-172; Gabled (n 14) 1030-1032. For a somewhat different approach, insisting on the fact that the Commission's legal responsibility ends once funds have been disbursed to national authorities, and on potential mismatches between the Commission's strict legal responsibility, and its broader political responsibility, see Antonio-Martin Porras-Gomez, ‘The EU Recovery Instrument and the Constitutional Implications of its Expenditure’, *EuConst*, 2023, 10, 18-19.

²⁴ Lilyanova (n 18) 3-4.

protection of the Union’s financial interests and guarantee that RRF funds are used in compliance with applicable EU and national laws (including procurement and state aid), but that “the Commission should be able to receive sufficient assurance from Member States in that regard.” In other words, the Member States and the Commission jointly ensure the protection of the EU’s financial interests, according to their respective responsibilities.²⁵ Supranational and national systems of audit and control therefore play a key and complementary role in the oversight of recovery funds, which requires sharing responsibilities, which we address in the next section.

16.3 Shared control and audit responsibilities between the Commission and the Member States for the sound management of recovery funds

Interactions between the Commission and the Member States on control systems take place when the NRRP is adopted (3.1), during the disbursement process (3.2), and *ex post* in the event of a serious irregularity that requires some correction (3.3).

16.3.1 Evaluation of national control systems through the NRRP’s adoption process

As stated in Article 22(1) of the RRF Regulation, Member States are responsible for the sound management of EU funding as well as the protection of the financial interests of the Union, and must ensure that recovery funds are used in accordance with applicable Union and national law. However, the Commission assumes a “residual responsibility”, as it ensures that adequate national control systems are in place to protect these principles.²⁶

Prior to the adoption of their national plan, Member States had to describe their internal control and audit systems. NRRPs detailed the processes aimed to collect and provide access to data, to prevent, detect, and correct serious irregularities, and to avoid double funding.²⁷ Responsible national authorities and their roles also had to be clearly identified.²⁸ The RRF Regulation also confirmed the possibility to rely on regular budget management systems.²⁹ Although a few Member States decided to create a new framework, a majority of them preferred to use pre existing structures.³⁰

An important part of the assessment of draft NRRPs by the Commission covered audit and control systems. The assessment method indeed includes a criterion commanding the Commission to check whether “arrangements proposed by the Member State concerned are expected to prevent, detect, and correct” serious irregularities and double funding.³¹ More specifically, the guidelines provided by the RRF Regulation for the assessment of national plans require close evaluation, among others, of the robustness and adequateness of processes and structures, the “segregation of relevant functions”, or the “legal empowerment and administrative capacity” of the actors responsible for audit and control systems.³²

²⁵ European Court of Auditors ‘Design of the Commission’s control system for the RRF. Assurance and accountability gap remains at EU level in the new delivery model, despite extensive work being planned’, Special Report 07/2023, March 2023, 6-7.

²⁶ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 27.

²⁷ RRF Regulation, Recital 54, Article 18(4)(r), Annex V; Kreith and Arwidi (n 22) 172.

²⁸ European Court of Auditors ‘Annual report on the implementation of the EU budget for the 2021 financial year’, July 2022, 262; Lilyanova (n 18) 4.

²⁹ RRF Regulation, Article 22(1).

³⁰ Ivana Maletić, ‘Obtaining a full picture of the RRF – a multidimensional puzzle requiring various ECA efforts’, in European Court of Auditors, ‘The EU Recovery and Resilience Facility: a jump to a resilient Europe?’, *ECA Journal*, 2/2022, 58; Lilyanova (n 17) 4.

³¹ RRF Regulation, Art 19(3)(j).

³² RRF Regulation, Annex V, 2.10.

Interestingly, only two ratings were available for this criterion (“A” for “adequate arrangements” and “C” for “insufficient arrangements”), unlike for most other criteria. This approach aims at preventing the validation of a plan and the allocation of funding in case of inadequacy.³³ Gradation is thus excluded with regard to the sound management of EU funds and the protection of the Union’s financial interests,³⁴ hereby underlining the importance granted to solid national control and audit systems.

During the assessment of NRRPs, the Commission requested additional information and commitments on important features of the control systems for every member state. It requested a majority of Member States to add milestones to be complied with before the first payment to solve the weaknesses identified in national control and audit systems, such as “the absence of formal legal mandates for the bodies in charge of implementing and auditing funds”; or the “lack of a clear audit strategy or anti-fraud measures.”³⁵ The Hungarian and Polish plans are quite illustrative as both include “supermilestones” on national anti-corruption frameworks, fraud prevention, transparency of public procurement, or judicial independence to ensure adequate national control systems, all to be complied with before any payment under the RRF can be made.³⁶ In a different category, the Belgian plan contains important milestones devoted to sound financial management regarding the creation of a repository system, ensuring good data collection and the coordination of federal and regional control systems, which also had to be fulfilled prior to the validation of the first payment.³⁷

Once NRRPs are adopted by the Council of the EU, commitments and arrangements are written down in all financing agreements concluded between the Commission and the Member State concerned.³⁸ Annex I of these agreements lists the requirements relating to national control systems, such as the functions and features of the designated authorities, the verification and audit procedures to be conducted against serious irregularities and double funding, or the possibility for EU bodies to access the collected data.³⁹ Article 11 of financing agreements details the Commission’s and Member State’s obligations for the protection of the Union’s financial interests: in particular, the Member State shall “regularly check” that related European and national rules are complied with, “take appropriate measures to prevent, detect, and correct” serious irregularities, “collect and ensure access” to data.⁴⁰

The RRF Regulation states that the Commission shall make its data-mining and risk-scoring tool called ARACHNE available to national authorities for a smooth collection, access and analysis of data and shall aim at a “general application by the Member States.”⁴¹ This tool would help to identify the recovery funds under risk of serious irregularities, and thus to protect the EU’s financial interests. Yet, even if recommended by the ECA in a special

³³ RRF Regulation, Annex V, 3(c).

³⁴ Kreith and Arwidi (n 22) 173; Gadbled (n 14) 1035-36.

³⁵ European Court of Auditors (n 27) 271; Lilyanova (n 18) 4 and Annex I.

³⁶ See Council implementing Decision of 5 December 2022 on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Hungary (ST 15447 2022 INIT), recitals 55-63, article 2(3); Council implementing Decision of 14 June 2022 on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Poland (ST 9728 2022 INIT), recitals 43-52, article 2(3).

³⁷ See Council implementing Decision of 13 July 2021 on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Belgium (ST 10161/2021), recital 43, article 2(3), milestones 209 and 210.

³⁸ RRF Regulation, Art 22(2)

³⁹ For instance, see Recovery and Resilience Facility Financing Agreement between the Commission and the Republic of Latvia, 06.09.2021, 15-16.

⁴⁰ For instance, see Recovery and Resilience Facility Financing Agreement between the Commission and the Republic of Latvia (n 38) 28-9.

⁴¹ RRF Regulation, Recital 54, Article 22(4)

report,⁴² its use by national authorities is not mandatory as long as the required information is readily accessible by domestic and EU bodies, which led some Member States to rely on their own systems.⁴³

The ECA has checked the Commission's assessment of monitoring, control and audit arrangements proposed by Member States. The ECA underlined that the Commission flagged relevant "gaps or deficiencies requiring additional measures to be implemented before the first payment."⁴⁴ Overall, it acknowledged and validated the comprehensive and thorough evaluation by the Commission, but also warned that it was partly based on systems "not yet in place at the time of the assessment", which limited the analysis of their "administrative capacity" and created "the risk that the financial interests of the EU are not sufficiently protected until these milestones are fulfilled."⁴⁵ It therefore recommended the Commission's close scrutiny of milestones related to control systems and encouraged the use of ARACHNE by national authorities.⁴⁶ In following reports, the ECA recalled that the absence of fully functional control systems before NRRPs become operational posed a risk for the regularity of expenditure and required later verification.⁴⁷ The Commission considered in turn that *ex ante* assessment of control systems takes place, in essence, before their full implementation, as is the case for other EU programmes, and does not create a specific risk for the financial interests of the Union since these milestones must be complied with before the first payment, with the additional possibility of sanctions in case of breach of obligations.⁴⁸

Following the assessment, update, and adoption of NRRP provisions regarding control systems, the Commission must confirm the satisfactory fulfilment of audit and control milestones to allow the first payments. For those assessed in 2022, the ECA did not raise any issues.⁴⁹ To further confirm the implementation of these frameworks, the Commission also uses its audit capacity: at the end of 2022, 16 system audits were conducted, covering 64 national actors, leading to recommendations when necessary.⁵⁰ Yet, while control milestones were considered fulfilled in the *ex ante* assessment phase, the Commission found, in the *ex post* phase, some weaknesses in the reporting and control systems of Italy and Croatia.⁵¹ This example illustrates the importance of payment request assessments and *ex post* audits.

16.3.2 The performance of control and audit in relation to payment requests

The Commission's and the Member States' oversight responsibilities are also manifested at the payment stage. When submitting a payment request, the national authority must provide

⁴² European Court of Auditors 'The Commission's assessment of national recovery and resilience plans – Overall appropriate but implementation risks remain', Special Report 21/2022, 21.07.22, 47

⁴³ Kreith and Arwidi (n 22) 173; Lilyanova (n 18) 7-8; Plamen Petrov, 'Anti-fraud set-up in the cohesion landscape', in European Court of Auditors, 'Cohesion and Next Generation EU – concord or clash?', *ECA Journal*, 1/2022, 81.

⁴⁴ European Court of Auditors (n 41) 47.

⁴⁵ European Court of Auditors (n 41) 44-45, 47.

⁴⁶ European Court of Auditors (n 41) 53.

⁴⁷ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 15-16; European Court of Auditors 'Annual Report on the implementation of the EU budget for the 2022 financial year', Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, July 2023, 360.

⁴⁸ Replies of the European Commission to the European Court of Auditors' Special Report. European Court of Auditor's Special Report 'The Commission's assessment of national recovery and resilience plans', 29.08.22, 9.

⁴⁹ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 450, 457.

⁵⁰ Replies of the European Commission to the European Court of Auditors' Special Report 'Design of the Commission's control system for the RRF', 08.03.2023, 3.

⁵¹ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 353-54.

the Commission with the following elements: i) evidence of compliance with the milestones and targets listed in the installment concerned; ii) a management declaration; and iii) a summary of audits.⁵²

The management declaration must confirm that funds were used for their intended purpose; that the information submitted with the request is complete, accurate and reliable; and that the control systems put in place give the necessary assurances that the funds were managed in accordance with all applicable rules, most notably on avoidance of conflicts of interests, fraud prevention, corruption and double funding.⁵³

As to audits summaries, the Commission has provided guidance for their preparation, defining the type of audits expected from national auditors and specifying the information to be included in these documents.⁵⁴ Audits summaries should also indicate identified weaknesses and related corrective actions.⁵⁵ A template is annexed to each financing agreement concluded between the Commission and the Member State concerned.⁵⁶ Moreover, bilateral meetings and exchanges take place between the Commission and national audit authorities to improve the quality and coverage of their audit work.⁵⁷

Once a payment request is submitted, the Commission's preliminary assessment checks whether milestones and targets have been satisfactorily fulfilled according to the evidence provided. It also relies on the content of the management declaration and the summary of audits to confirm the coherence and accuracy of the information, even though it can conduct fact-finding missions of its own if required.⁵⁸

Once payments are allowed, *ex post* audit powers of the Commission play a significant role. A lively debate in this regard concerns the reversal of milestones and targets previously fulfilled. The ECA warned several times about the absence of guidance on the definition, monitoring, financial impact as well as consequences of such a reversal, creating a risk that the Commission fails identifying such situations.⁵⁹ The Commission considered such risk was low due to the continuous monitoring and interactions between national authorities and the Commission's geographical desks.⁶⁰ Yet, it accepted the ECA's recommendation to develop procedures to address reversals in a consistent manner⁶¹ and to revise its *ex post* audit procedure to codify checks on previously fulfilled targets and milestones,⁶² which it has since then started to undertake.⁶³ The ECA attested that a case of reversal took place with a target of the first payment to Italy, but the Commission did not agree with the ECA, arguing that an event outside of the control of the Member States, such as natural disaster, does not mean a reversal has occurred.⁶⁴

⁵² RRF Regulation, Article 22(2)(c) and 24.

⁵³ RRF Regulation, Article 22(2)(c)(i).

⁵⁴ European Commission, 'Guidance to Member States for the preparation of the summary of audits under the RRF', 27.9.2021.

⁵⁵ RRF Regulation, Article 22(2)(c)(ii).

⁵⁶ For instance, see Recovery and Resilience Facility Financing Agreement between the Commission and the Republic of Latvia (n 38) 19-20.

⁵⁷ European Commission (n 49) 5.

⁵⁸ Lilyanova (n 18) 5.

⁵⁹ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 26, 32; European Court of Auditors (n 46) 360.

⁶⁰ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 26.

⁶¹ European Commission (n 49) 6.

⁶² European Court of Auditors (n 46) 360.

⁶³ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 456, 459.

⁶⁴ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 454-455.

Responsibility for *ex post* audits of recovery funds within the Commission lies with DG ECFIN. Based on the RRF audit strategy adopted in 2021, it performs several types of audits complementary to the Member States'.⁶⁵ First, audits on milestones and targets verify their successful fulfillment *ex post*, following the *ex ante* check conducted at the payment request stage. They concern all milestones and targets considered "high risk", and a maximum of "medium risk."⁶⁶ In addition, system audits control that national systems collect and store adequate and reliable data and take measures to avoid serious irregularities, double funding, and serious breaches of agreements. This category should target each Member State at least once by the end of 2023.⁶⁷ The Commission has undertaken 16 system audits on the protection of the Union's financial interests in 2022, covering 16 coordinating bodies and 48 implementing bodies. Lastly, *ad hoc* audits are conducted on a risk-specific basis.

Another heated debate concerning the Commission's *ex post* strategy focused on the review of compliance with European and national rules. According to the ECA, despite the rapid development of a solid control system by the Commission, the lack of such a verification represents a "EU-level assurance gap" and a risk for the Union's financial interests.⁶⁸ The Commission nevertheless contests this assessment, recalling that the responsibility to check compliance with EU and national rules (such as public procurement rules) lies with the Member States, although its system audits additionally check that they perform their duties in this respect.⁶⁹ In fact, it can verify compliance with European and domestic law "only to the extent that this is included in the conditions attached to the milestone or target."⁷⁰

16.3.3 The corrective mechanisms available at Union level

As a matter of principle, Member States are to comply with milestones and targets in a timely manner, and to use an effective internal control system to prevent, detect, and correct serious irregularities or double funding, recovering amounts wrongly paid or incorrectly used.⁷¹ When these obligations are not fulfilled, the Commission must intervene. The RRF allows for two types of financial corrections focusing either on non-compliance with milestones and targets, or on non-correction of serious irregularities or double funding affecting the Union's financial interests. We analyse these two types of financial corrections in turn.

On the one hand, the RRF Regulation sets up a procedure for cases of non-compliance with milestones and targets. In case of non-satisfactory fulfillment of relevant milestones and targets, requests will not be honored and payment will be suspended. The suspension will only be lifted once "the Member State concerned has taken the necessary measures to ensure a satisfactory fulfillment of the milestones and targets."⁷² If the Member State fails to act within a period of six months, the Commission is to reduce the amount of the financial contribution (or the loan) proportionately, having given national authorities the possibility to submit observations.⁷³ Ultimately, if there is no progress on any milestone or target in the 18 months following the adoption of the Council implementing decision, the amount of the financial

⁶⁵ Lilyanova (n 18) 6.

⁶⁶ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 24-25.

⁶⁷ European Court of Auditors 'Institutions' replies to the annual report on the implementation of the EU budget for the 2021 financial year', Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, July 2022, 342.

⁶⁸ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 5, 17-18, 32.

⁶⁹ European Commission (n 49) 3, 6.

⁷⁰ Céline Gauer 'The Recovery and Resilience Facility, An Instrument built for Performance' in European Court of Auditors, 'The EU Recovery and Resilience Facility: a jump to a resilient Europe?', *ECA Journal*, 2/2022, 27.

⁷¹ RRF Regulation, Article 22.

⁷² RRF Regulation, Article 24(6).

⁷³ RRF Regulation, Article 24(8).

contribution is decommitted, agreements are terminated, and pre-financing must be fully recovered from the Member State concerned.⁷⁴ In February 2023, the Commission published its suspension methodology,⁷⁵ detailing the rules to calculate amounts to be suspended or reduced. Doing so, it finally acted upon calls from its own Internal Audit System⁷⁶ and the ECA,⁷⁷ which had also deplored the uncertainty caused by the lack of “price tags” associated with each milestone and target, but above all the initial absence of such methodology as the lack of “an important element of the RRF control system ensuring the regularity of RRF payments”.⁷⁸

On the other hand, the RRF Regulation foresees the right of the Commission to sanction serious irregularities, double funding, or serious violations of financing and loan agreements. The Commission can indeed reduce financial support provided under the RRF, recover funds already disbursed, or ask for early repayment of the loan if the Union’s financial interests are threatened by issues of fraud, corruption, and conflicts of interests which have not been corrected by the Member State, or by the breach of an obligation in an agreement.⁷⁹ In such cases, the Commission must abide by the principle of proportionality, most notably by considering the seriousness of the irregularity, and give national authorities the opportunity to present observations. Financing agreements set the rules to calculate the amount of the financial penalty and provide for flat-rate corrections for serious breaches of an obligation due to the weakness of the national control systems.⁸⁰

In this regard, the ECA recommended the development of internal guidance on the application of these flat rates to ensure transparency and consistency.⁸¹ Yet, the Commission rejected the request, arguing that the criteria are already defined in financing agreements and that any correction would be accompanied by a clear justification.⁸² The ECA found one case of double funding in Slovakia as a milestone was partly funded by the European Social Fund. Even with zero estimated costs under the RRF, the ECA recalled that recovery funds were disbursed following the fulfillment of this milestone,⁸³ while the Commission stressed that the RRF Regulation links the concept to cost, hence the absence of double funding in this case.⁸⁴

We agree with Gadbled that the first corrective mechanism described in the above provides a powerful incentive structure for the improvement of the Member States’ control and audit systems, independent from the actual risks their deficiencies pose for the Union’s financial interests.⁸⁵ Indeed, since milestones and targets pertaining to the improvement of national control and audit frameworks are determined before the NRRP’s adoption and should be complied with before the first payment request, access to all RRF funds can be withheld

⁷⁴ RRF Regulation, Article 24(9).

⁷⁵ European Commission, Communication – RRF: Two years on, COM(2023)99, 21.2.2023, pp. 10-11, 15-17.

⁷⁶ Manfred Kraff, ‘The European Commission’s Internal Audit Service: evolving to meet the challenges of today’ in European Court of Auditors, ‘The EU Recovery and Resilience Facility: a jump to a resilient Europe?’, *ECA Journal*, 2/2022, 38.

⁷⁷ European Court of Auditors (n 27) 271, 276; European Court of Auditors (n 24) 23-24. See also, Nikolaos Kylonis and Judit Ozoski, ‘The ECA’s Statement of Assurance audit of the RRF’ in European Court of Auditors, ‘The EU Recovery and Resilience Facility: a jump to a resilient Europe?’, *ECA Journal*, 2/2022, 76.

⁷⁸ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 23.

⁷⁹ RRF Regulation, Article 22(5), Recital 53.

⁸⁰ For instance, see Recovery and Resilience Facility Financing Agreement between the Commission and the Republic of Latvia (n 38) 12-13.

⁸¹ European Court of Auditors (n 24) 33.

⁸² European Commission (n 49) 7.

⁸³ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 348.

⁸⁴ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 449, 454.

⁸⁵ Gadbled (n 14) 1039.

regardless of the materialization of such risk. The second category of financial corrections follows a different, complementary logic, with a more targeted, proportional response to concrete irregularities, and actual threats posed to the EU's financial interests.

On that last note, one should keep in mind that the corrective mechanisms of the RRF are completed by the new spending conditionality instrument set up by Regulation 2020/2092, which allows for the adoption of financial measures in case of breaches of the principles of the rule of law which “affect or seriously risk affecting the sound financial management of the Union budget or the financial interests of the Union in a sufficiently direct way.”⁸⁶ The scope of this mechanism is transversal, and covers all budgetary programs of the EU, including the RRF. Consequently, recovery funds could be targeted by financial measures adopted under this Regulation.⁸⁷

16.4 The oversight capacity and involvement of EU external control bodies in the RRF

The Union can rely on the support of other European actors for the sound management of recovery funds, fostering coordination between external and internal auditors. The initial proposal for the RRF Regulation did not mention the role of Union bodies other than the Commission and the Council of the EU. The ECA however recommended, in its Opinion 6/20 on the proposal, that its right of audit be clearly recognized in a specific provision.⁸⁸ This issue was taken up by the European Parliament and, as a result, the final RRF Regulation, requires financial agreements to expressly authorize, in line with Article 129 of the Financial Regulation, the Commission, but also the ECA, OLAF and EPPO to exert their control and audit rights over all final recipients of recovery funds.⁸⁹ The involvement of these last three bodies in the oversight of recovery funds is examined below.

16.3.3 The ECA's audit work and challenges related to the RRF

The RRF naturally comes within the wide mandate of the ECA. In line with Article 287 TFEU, the ECA is entitled to audit any expenditure under the RRF, non-repayable support and loans, through compliance and performance audits.⁹⁰ Concretely, the ECA's assessment of control systems may determine the existence of weaknesses in the Commission's or the Member States' control and audit activity as well as in the availability of information on the final recipients or contractors or in record-keeping, thereby contributing to the identification of risks affecting the sound management of recovery funds.⁹¹

⁸⁶ Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2092 of the European Parliament and the Council of 16 December 2020 on a general regime of conditionality for the protection of the Union budget [2020] OJ L 433I, Article 4(1).

⁸⁷ See Chapter 13 of this volume on rule of law spending conditionality.

⁸⁸ European Court of Auditors, Opinion No 6/2020 (pursuant to Article 287(4) and 322(1)(a), TFEU) concerning the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Recovery and Resilience Facility (COM(2020) 408) 2020/C 350/01, OJ C 350, para. 22.

⁸⁹ RRF Regulation, Article 22(2)(e), Recitals 55 and 72. For a concrete example, see Recovery and Resilience Facility Financing Agreement between the Commission and the Republic of Latvia (n 38) art 12, which confirms that, to the extent of their competences, ECA, OLAF and EPPO can “carry out reviews, checks, audits, and investigations”, access any relevant premise or data, or “take every appropriate measures to facilitate their work.

⁹⁰ On this distinction, see Paul Stephenson, ‘Reconciling Audit and Evaluation? The Shift to Performance and Effectiveness at the European Court of Auditors’ (2015) 6 *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 81.

⁹¹ European Court of Auditors (n 46) 363.

The work of an independent external auditor brings value and credibility to the work done by European and national actors.⁹² Yet, the ECA has limited resources and inevitably had to constrain its work to certain aspects of the RRF. The Facility is a real challenge for the ECA. Its size, combined with its disbursement pace, and its organization around hundreds of milestones and targets and payment requests, represent a significant increase for the workload of ECA and its five audit chambers.⁹³ Yet, the internal organization of the ECA has not changed except for the creation of a taskforce to coordinate all teams involved in NGEU-related tasks.⁹⁴ Besides the 900 usual employees, only 20 positions were created for the related audit work,⁹⁵ while the ECA president had called for 40 temporary contracts and more resources for a thorough analysis.⁹⁶

The ECA confirmed in its annual work programmes its intention to publish 12 audit reports examining NGEU, mainly covering the RRF.⁹⁷ Several special reports, on which this chapter heavily draws, have already been published, addressing for instance the Commission's assessment of NRRPs (21/2022) or the design of the Commission's control system for the RRF (07/2023). Upcoming publications will, among others, focus on the issue of double funding and Member States' RRF control systems.⁹⁸ A review is expected in 2025 to "take stock of the ECA's audit work on the RRF and to flag risks, challenges and opportunities."⁹⁹

In its work, the ECA also cooperates with the Supreme Audit Institutions (SAIs) of the 27 Member States. The Contact Committee is an exchange platform for a common approach on audit and control of the RRF which regularly gathers the heads of SAIs and of the ECA. For example, a meeting was organised in 2021 with the help of the German and Belgian SAIs on auditing the implementation of NRRPs at EU and national levels.¹⁰⁰ In addition, the ECA provides RRF-related training.

The main challenge for the ECA's work regarding the RRF relates to the Statement of Assurance (SoA), and more generally, to its overall approach to auditing. The SoA is an annual report on the legality and regularity of EU payments in each major area of the EU budget based on compliance and performance audits. Yet, the functioning of the RRF forces the ECA to adapt the traditional audit approach of the SoA.¹⁰¹ Classically, the ECA assesses

⁹² Interview with Gašper Dovžan, State Secretary of Slovenia, by Gaston Moonen. 'EU integration for a shared space of common values', in European Court of Auditors, 'Cohesion and Next Generation EU – concord or clash?', *ECA Journal*, 1/2022, 42.

⁹³ Maletić (n 29) 56.

⁹⁴ Michele Zagordo, 'ECA and the RRF – where did we start, where are we now and... where are we heading?', in European Court of Auditors, 'The EU Recovery and Resilience Facility: a jump to a resilient Europe?', *ECA Journal*, 2/2022, 67-68.

⁹⁵ Interview with two experts on auditing cohesion funds – Franck Sébert, European Commission, and Juan Ignacio Gonzalez Bastero, ECA, by Gaston Moonen. 'Auditing EU cohesion funds – triggering policy improvement by joining forces', in European Court of Auditors, 'Cohesion and Next Generation EU – concord or clash?', *ECA Journal*, 1/2022, 68.

⁹⁶ János Allenbach-Ammann 'EU court of auditors calls for more resources during NGEU programme', Euractiv, 26.10.2021 <<https://www.euractiv.com/section/economy-jobs/news/eu-court-of-auditors-calls-for-more-resources-during-ngeu-programme/>> accessed 27 December 2023.

⁹⁷ European Court of Auditors, 'Our activities in 2022. Annual Activity Report of the European Court of Auditors', 2023, 11.

⁹⁸ European Court of Auditors, '2023+ Work Programme', 8.11.2022, 4-5.

⁹⁹ European Court of Auditors, '2024+ Work Programme', 12.12.2023, 16.

¹⁰⁰ European Court of Auditors, 'Our activities in 2021. Annual Activity Report of the European Court of Auditors', 2022, 44.

¹⁰¹ Lilyanova (n 18) 7; Interview with Iliana Ivanova, ECA Member and Chair of the ECA audit chamber Investment for cohesion, growth and inclusion by Gaston Moonen. 'Auditing EU cohesion policy', in European Court of Auditors, 'Cohesion and Next Generation EU – concord or clash?', *ECA Journal*, 1/2022, 54.

compliance with all relevant EU and national rules to evaluate the eligibility of the projects and beneficiaries, and of the costs incurred. Audit work under the RRF consists of “assessing whether the Commission has gathered sufficient and appropriate evidence to justify the ‘satisfactory’ fulfilment of milestones and targets.”¹⁰² Such a task is obviously more complex considering the discretion the Commission enjoys in that context. Moreover, compliance with EU and national rules remains the Member State’s responsibility. Cases of non-compliance with EU or national rules will be identified by the ECA as issues but will not question the disbursement of funds,¹⁰³ while the detection of serious irregularities (fraud, corruption, conflict of interests or double funding) will entail an evaluation of the impact on the RRF payment.¹⁰⁴

16.3.3 The investigation capacity of the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) and of the European Public Prosecutor’s Office (EPPO) over recovery funds

The role of OLAF¹⁰⁵ is to conduct independent administrative investigations on fraud involving EU funds.¹⁰⁶ Its recommendations to launch prosecutions can be followed up or not by the competent European or national authorities. When it comes to the RRF, Article 22(2)(e) of the RRF Regulation has explicitly confirmed OLAF’s competence and key role. As a matter of fact, OLAF very early warned against the big risk of fraud in the use of recovery funds.¹⁰⁷ It has been involved in the screening and assessment of NRRPs, providing “its input on whether the control and audit mechanisms described in the plans were solid enough to protect the EU’s financial interests, with the aim of ensuring that the measures were as concrete and operational as possible.”¹⁰⁸ While implementation of NRRPs is ongoing, OLAF conducts administrative investigations on RRF-related expenditure and financially supports Member States for anti-fraud measures through a dedicated instrument, the Union Anti-Fraud Programme.¹⁰⁹ It also advises the Commission on a distinct RRF anti-fraud strategy and on the anti-fraud features of the Member States’ management systems.¹¹⁰

Operational since 2021, the EPPO is responsible “for investigating, prosecuting and bringing to judgment the perpetrators of, and accomplices to, criminal offences affecting the financial interests of the Union.”¹¹¹ Therefore, EPPO is competent to investigate and prosecute criminal

¹⁰² Kylonis and Ozoszki (n 76) 76.

¹⁰³ Such cases, once signaled, may however lead to administrative and legal proceedings.

¹⁰⁴ Kylonis and Ozoszki (n 76) 75.

¹⁰⁵ In general, on the role of OLAF, and EPPO, in the protection of the Union’s financial interests, see Maurizio Bellacosa and Maurizia De Bellis, ‘The protection of the EU financial interests between administrative and criminal tools: OLAF and EPPO’, *CMLR*, 2023, 15-50.

¹⁰⁶ See Article 325 TFEU; Commission Decision of 28 April 1999 establishing the European Anti-fraud Office (OLAF) [1999] OJ L136; Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 September 2013 concerning investigations conducted by the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1073/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1074/1999 [2013] OJ L248.

¹⁰⁷ Sam Fleming and Michael Peel, ‘Fraud chief warns of big risk in policing 800bn EU recovery funds’, *Financial Times*, 17 June 2021.

¹⁰⁸ Kreith and Arwidi (n 22) 173.

¹⁰⁹ Kreith and Arwidi (n 22) 173.

¹¹⁰ European Commission (DG ECFIN), ‘Audit Strategy for the Recovery and Resilience Facility. RRF: Building Audit Assurance’, 15.10.2021, 19.

¹¹¹ Council Regulation (EU) 2017/1939 of 12 October 2017 implementing enhanced cooperation on the establishment of the European Public Prosecutor’s Office (‘the EPPO’) [2017] OJ L283, article 4. See also Article 86 TFEU.

activities related to recovery funds in the 22 participating Member States. The activities of EPPO in this regard are ensured by the 22 European Delegated Prosecutors under the supervision of the Central Office. In that it can initiate investigations and prosecutions on its own motion, its powers and autonomy are undeniably stronger than that of OLAF. Yet, a major limitation to the powers of EPPO flows from the fact that it originates from an enhanced cooperation. The new European prosecutor's prerogatives (unlike OLAF's) only apply to participating Member States, meaning that it has no jurisdiction over the five non-participating states, i.e. Denmark, Hungary, Ireland, Poland and Sweden.¹¹² This is certainly problematic in the case of Hungary and Poland, where risks of fraud and corruption have been deemed serious in view of rule of law backsliding in these countries. Some commentators had called the EU to make access to NGEU monies conditional upon accession to the EPPO, through the insertion of a dedicated milestone in their respective NRRPs.¹¹³ While these NRRPs contain, as seen *supra*, an important number of milestones and targets designed to ensure the effective protection of the Union's financial interests, this conditionality was ultimately not favored, most likely because its legal foundations were deemed too fragile.

The main strength of the EPPO when it comes to the RRF is its potential for cooperation with other EU actors. For instance, it signed a working arrangement with the ECA in 2021.¹¹⁴ Moreover, together with Europol, Eurojust, OLAF and 19 Member States, the EPPO participates to Operation Sentinel, an initiative designed to guarantee a coordinated response to "an expected wave of fraud" against recovery funds.¹¹⁵ More specifically with regard to the cooperation between OLAF and EPPO, the latter can be expected to take a leading role in the investigation of frauds due to its stronger prerogatives. The constant exchange of information between OLAF and EPPO aims to foster complementarity and avoid overlaps in the oversight of the RRF.¹¹⁶ While the EPPO focuses on suspected fraud or corruption, OLAF concentrates on irregularities and reports suspected criminal offenses to the EPPO.

16.4 Conclusion

Sound financial management has from the outset been a major concern for the architects of NGEU. The challenge has lain in finding an acceptable balance between macroeconomic performance and the protection of the Union's financial interests. In other words, how to ensure the swift implementation of the plan and rapid disbursement of NGEU monies, in order to maximize economic support to the recovery, while at the same time obtaining solid guarantees and assurances on the proper use of funds and securing the establishment of strong structures of audit and control? The result is a singular compromise, which this Chapter has sought to unveil. On the one hand, the RRF is implemented in direct management, with the Member States as direct beneficiaries, to ensure swift injection of the RRF funds in national economies. On the other, the recovery plan rests on an elaborate control and audit system, *à la*

¹¹² Costanza Di Francesco Maesa, 'Repercussions of the establishment of the EPPO via enhanced cooperation', *EU Crim*, 2017/3, 156-160.

¹¹³ See, for example, Daniel Gros, Steven Blockmans and Francesco Corti, 'Rule of law and the Next Generation EU recovery', CEPS Opinion, 15 October 2020.

¹¹⁴ EPPO, 'EPPO signs working arrangement with the European Court of Auditors', 3 September 2021, <https://www.eppo.europa.eu/en/news/eppo-signs-working-arrangement-european-court-auditors#:~:text=The%20European%20Public%20Prosecutor%27s%20Office,of%20protecting%20the%20EU%20budget>.

¹¹⁵ EUROPOL, 'New operation to protect Next Generation EU recovery funds', 15 October 2021, <https://www.europol.europa.eu/media-press/newsroom/news/new-operation-to-protect-next-generation-eu-recovery-funds>.

¹¹⁶ Petrov (n 42) 80.

shared management, which closely intertwines national and European apparatus, and that is articulated around different procedural phases. Indeed, this shared management combines *ex ante* and *ex post*, preventive and corrective mechanisms, and places national authorities and final recipients of recovery funds under tight and close scrutiny. The audit and control framework of NGEU and the RRF also involves, as external safeguards, other supranational actors, namely the ECA, the EPPO and OLAF. The Chapter has described the welcome oversight these actors have exercised over the Commission's and national authorities' audit work, and the productive interactions established in that context. Financial accountability under NGEU certainly presents a singular, complex, almost baroque, picture, but that seems, to a large extent, to be the price to pay for the unprecedentedness of NGEU as a political and budgetary initiative.

The audit and control framework is not, as we saw, without its challenges. Actor coordination and cooperation will be key. Moreover, NGEU puts EU and national audit and control systems under increased administrative pressure. While legal and procedural arrangements are in place, it is not entirely clear if the Union's and the Member States' control and audit bodies possess the material and human resources necessary to keep up with the surge in workload implied by NGEU. If the framework established appears *a priori* sound and reliable, it is only with hindsight that we will be able to judge how well it managed its core objectives to protect the Union's financial interests and prevent the historical post-pandemic recovery effort from being undermined by fraud, corruption and financial mismanagement.